

INNOVATIVE IN-WHEEL MOTOR DESIGN WITH INTEGRATED DIRECT COOLING AND MECHANICAL E-GEAR

EM-TECH

Relative power density increase [86%] and high maximum power [124 kW]

High specific torque [44,5 Nm/kg] and cost reduction [5,73 EUR/kW]

Design and performance values flexibility with the E-gear

CHALLENGES & SOLUTION:

EM-TECH project objectives addressed some novel, never before realized, technical solutions such as direct cooling in an IWM and an implementation of an electro-mechanical switch which takes advantage of Elaphe's dual winding design. Both of these solutions presented an architectural challenge and the final product displays an amazing accomplishment by the involved partners on the project, Elaphe Propulsion Technologies, University of Bath and Politecnica di Torino.

The EM-TECH IWM has a substantial power density increase compared to the baseline IWM and a very high specific torque level [44,5 Nm/kg], while simultaneously using magnets with less heavy-rare earth content [39% decrease]. In addition, a cost study was conducted and showed final product cost potential in the range of 5,73 EUR/kW.

IMPACT & NEXT STEPS:

EM-TECH IWM is a first design iteration in what might become a new State-of-Art for commercial In-Wheel motor. The direct cooling solution opened the doors towards completely new IWM architectures and is a concept that will be further explored due to its potential in power increase and cooling efficiency. The e-gear shows potential in different applications on the market and is already gaining interest because of its ability to either improve IWM's efficiency in a specific drive cycle or increase the power level.

Figure 1: In-wheel motor with e-gear

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